

The Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Environment on Employee Performance With Job Satisfaction As A Mediation: Case at *PT Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera*

Bayu Kurniawan Azlen ¹, I Ketut R. Sudiartha ², Henry Eryanto ³

Article history:

Received October 14, 2022; Accepted: December 20, 2022; Displayed Online: December 27, 2022; Published: December 30, 2022

Keywords

Abstract

Organizational Culture;
Work Environment;
Job Satisfaction;
Employee Performance;
PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera;

Employee performance is one of the most important component in the progress of the company. For this reason, an analysis of the variables that affect employee performance needs to be carried out. This study aims to determine the influence of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance either directly or indirectly through job satisfaction. The theory used in this research is organizational culture, work environment, job satisfaction, and employee performance. The method used in this research is quantitative using SEM PLS data analysis using smartpls software. The results of this study indicate that organizational culture and work environment have a positive and significant direct influence on employee performance. Furthermore, job satisfaction is also able to mediate the influence of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance.

1. Introduction

Human resources are an important component to support the progress of the company. With the development of the times, organizations are starting to realize that quality human resources are assets that cannot be replaced more than other assets such as material assets, money, machines (Rozarie, 2017). Human resources are a core factor in an organization, therefore, organizational management must be able to manage and develop their human resources which are very important for the organization (Krismiyati, 2017). The key to the success of an organization cannot be

¹Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email : bayuzazlen@gmail.com

²Professor at Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

³Professor at Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

separated from the performance of human resources who directly or indirectly participate in achieving organizational goals (Asharini, 2018).

Performance is an achievement produced by an employee or group of employees in carrying out their responsibilities. The performance is measured based on skills, experience and sincerity. Experts argue that employee performance has a close relationship with organizational performance because the achievement of organizational goals cannot be separated from employee performance. This is because employees play the most active role in trying to achieve the goals of an organization (Hasibuan, 2016).

One of the goals of organizational management is to improve the performance of its employees. However, PT Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera experienced a problem that is often faced by many organizations in running their organization, that is the lack of employee performance. The following is the employee performance data of *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera*.

Table 1
Performance Data of *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera*

No	Division	Scale Rating 1 - 4			
		Jul - Sep 2021	Oct- Dec 2021	Jan - Mar 2022	Apr - Jun 2022
1	<i>Human Resources</i>	3,9	3,8	3,2	3,1
2	<i>Broadcast</i>	3.4	3,7	3,9	3,3
3	<i>Creative</i>	3.5	3,9	3.6	3,8
4	<i>Business Development</i>	3,9	3.2	3,8	3,4
5	<i>Marketing</i>	3,7	3,9	3,3	3,2
6	<i>Finance</i>	3.2	3,3	3.3	3,1

Source: (*PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera*, 2022)

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* experienced a decline in performance in several divisions and others showed unstable performance. This can be seen in the human resources division which experienced a decline from July to June 2022. Then, for the broadcast division, there was a decline at some time, that is in October-December 2021 and in April-June 2022. Furthermore, for the creative division, it can be seen that employee performance is not stable, it can be seen from the ups and downs of employee performance in the last one year period. Furthermore, the creative division and the business development division also experienced unstable employee performance in the past year. Then, the marketing division has decreased since entering 2022. Furthermore, the finance division has had a less than good performance in the last year with the lowest rating among other divisions.

Employee performance is influenced by several factors, including organizational culture. According to Rivai (2012) organizational culture is a system that is used as a benchmark or guide to the behavior of activities in the company and can direct employees to achieve the goals of the company. Organizational culture is also a belief held by the company that becomes the mindset and values that are understood, inspired and practiced by employees in the company, so that the system or pattern gives its own meaning which becomes the basis for the rules of behavior in the company.

In addition to organizational culture, the work environment also affects employee performance. According to Pranitasari (2019), the work environment is a condition in the workplace that is both

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

physical and non-physical and can have an influence on employee performance. Physical environment such as working conditions, company infrastructure and administration owned by the company. While the non-physical work environment is the relationship between workers and working conditions. Therefore, organizational management must be responsive to what is happening in the work environment, so that employees feel comfortable physical and non-physical work environment. When the work environment can be enjoyed by employees, then not only will the performance increase but the job satisfaction of the employees will also increase. This is because, employee job satisfaction can increase when employees can easily get the information they need to do their jobs and they feel comfortable with the environment around them (Nugroho, 2013).

The influence of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance can also be mediated by job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is the emotional state of employees who feel happy or unhappy about their work. Employees do not feel satisfaction when their expectations are not met. Broadly speaking, job satisfaction is how employees feel about the organization where they work (Munandar, 2012). When the expectations and job satisfaction of an employee have been achieved, the employee's performance will also increase (Devi, 2009).

Several previous studies related to the influence of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with employee satisfaction as a mediating variable have been carried out several times. First, research conducted by Wicaksono et al., (2021) and Jie (2020) states that organizational culture affects employee performance. Then, research conducted by Rizky (2020) and Sharma (2017) states that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Furthermore, research conducted by Parashakti (2020) and Dheviests (2020) states that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Then, research conducted by Taheri (2020) and Andriany (2019) stated that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Furthermore, research conducted by Wijaya (2018) and Hendro (2018) states that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Then, research conducted by Putri (2020) and Feri (2020) stated that job satisfaction was able to mediate the influence of organizational culture on employee performance. And research conducted by Kurniawan (2020) and Kusumastuti (2019) states that job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance.

Based on the background description and several previous studies that have been described above, the urgency related to the analysis of factors that affect employee performance needs to be carried out. For this reason, this study aims to determine the influence of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance, either directly or indirectly through job satisfaction.

2. Materials and Methods

The type of research used in this research is quantitative. The population used in this study were all employees at *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* as many as 120 people. Then, for the research sample, the researcher uses the type of probability sampling, that is, all of the population is likely to be the sample. This is done when the population is relatively small. Based on the explanation above, the sample in this study is the entire population taken, that is all employees of *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* with a total of 120 employees. However, after the questionnaires were distributed, only 107 questionnaires were considered feasible and qualified. So that, the sample in this study was 107 respondents.

The types and sources of data used in this study are primary data. Primary data is data obtained directly by the author from the first source for a specific purpose so that the data collected is more reliable and objective. The primary data used in this study was obtained through distributing questionnaires to all employees of *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera*.

Data collection techniques used in this study were through questionnaires and literature study. In this study the questionnaire used in the form of a Likert scale. The Likert scale is a psychometric scale that is commonly used in questionnaires, and is the most widely used scale in survey research. Then, the literature study was obtained from various sources relevant to the theme under study, that is from journals, books, and so on.

The variables used in this study are independent variables, dependent variable, and mediating variable. The independent variables consist of organizational culture (X1) and work environment (X2). The dependent variable consists of employee performance (Y). And the mediating variable consists of job satisfaction (Z). The following is a more detailed explanation regarding the operationalization of variables.

Table 2
Operationalization of Variables

Variables	Definition	Dimension	Source
Organizational Culture (X1)	Furnham and Gunter (1993) in Armstrong (2006) define organizational culture as a way of behaving and values that exist within the organization, or simply how employees do things in the organization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Details • Innovate • Team orientation • Result orientation • Aggressive • Stable 	(Napitupulu, 2018)
Work Environment (X2)	The work environment is everything that is in the workplace and can affect the performance of the organization (Robbins, 2002).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relations between employees • Noise • Work Regulations • Explanation • Air circulation • Security 	(Yuliantari, 2020)
Employee Performance (Y)	Leonardo (2015) defines employee performance as the result of employees in the form of quality and quantity of their work, based on individuals or groups in carrying out their duties.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work quality • Quantity of work • Work reliability • Work attitude 	(Yuliantari, 2020)
Job Satisfaction (Z)	Job satisfaction is the feeling of the extent to which an employee likes the work they do, it is an individual's assessment of the work being carried out (Weiss, 2002)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wages • The work itself • Work colleague • Superior • Promotion 	(Changgriawan, 2017)

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

Furthermore, the data analysis technique used is the Structure Equation Modeling (SEM) method with SmartPLS software as a tool in data processing and analysis. This software is used because the number of samples required in the analysis is relatively small. The use of SmartPLS is highly recommended when the researcher has a limited number of samples while the model being built is complex.

3. Results and Discussions

Characteristics of Respondents

Table 3
Overview of Respondents by Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	< 19	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	19-29	35	32.7	32.7	36.4
	30-39	45	42.1	42.1	78.5
	40-50	15	14	14	92.5
	> 50	8	7.5	7.5	100
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 3 above, it is known that the respondents aged 30-39 years were 45 respondents or 42.1%, then the second position was respondents with an age range of 19-29 years as many as 35 respondents or 32.7%, it is known that these two age ranges are dominated by Generation Z and Millennials. These generations are a group that was born and grew up with technological developments so that they are known as a generation that is technology literate and also proficient in operating the internet for work, study, or other things. So, in this case, the company will optimize its young employees as operational employees to support the company's growth. This is because, the younger generation is considered richer in innovation, likes challenges, and is also energetic, so that it will certainly provide benefits in terms of company operations.

Table 4
General Description of Respondents by Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	59	55.1	55.1	55.1
	Female	48	44.9	44.9	100
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 4 above, it is known that the characteristics of the respondents are dominated by male as many as 59 respondents or 55.1% while female as many as 48 respondents or 44.9%. This shows that there are more male employees than female employees. Men are usually synonymous with public work so that in terms of quantity, there are indeed more. However, the difference in quantity between

male employees and female employees is only slightly (10.2%), so that in this case, public work can be accessed by anyone, both men and women. This is what makes the number of male and female employees at *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* is not much different.

Table 5
Overview of Respondents Based on Education Level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	68	63.5	63.5	63.5
	Postgraduate	26	24.3	24.3	87.8
	Senior High School	13	12.2	12.2	100
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 5 above, out of 107 respondents, 68 respondents (63.5%) had a bachelor's degree, 26 respondents (24.3%) had a master's degree, and 13 respondents (12.2%) had a high school education. Thus, the majority of respondents are those who have the last education of bachelor. This is because some jobs are dominated by requirements for bachelor and postgraduate, and only a small number of jobs can be filled by high school graduates.

Table 6
Overview of Respondents by Income Level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<1.000.000	-	-	-	-
	1.000.000-3.000.000	12	11.2	11.2	11.2
	3.000.001 – 5.000.000	51	47.7	47.7	58.9
	5.000.001-10.000.000	35	32.7	32.7	91.6
	>10.000.000	9	8.4	8.4	100
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 6 above that of the 107 respondents, 51 respondents (47.7%) have an income of 3,000,001-5,000,000, 35 respondents (32.7%) have an income of 5,000,001-10,000,000, 12 respondents (11,2%) have income of 1,000,000-3,000,000, and 9 respondents (8,4%) have income >10,000,000. So, the most respondents are those who have an income of 3,000,001-5,000,000.

Table 7
Overview of Respondents Based on Length of Work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<1 Year	10	9.3	9.3	9.3
	1 – 5 Years	37	34.7	34.7	44

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

	5 – 10 Years	48	44.8	44.8	88.8
	>10 Years	12	11.2	11.2	100
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 7 above that out of 107 respondents, 48 respondents (44.8%) have worked at *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* for 5-10 years. Then, 37 respondents (34.7%) have worked at *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* for 1-5 years. Furthermore, 12 respondents (11.2%) have worked at *PT. Teknologi Abadi Sejahtera* for > 10 years. And, 10 respondents (9.3%) have worked for < 1 year. Thus, the majority of respondents are those who have a working period of 5-10 years.

Variable Descriptive Analysis

Table 8
Variable Descriptive Statistics

Indicator	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Organizational Culture (X1)	107	1	5	4,267	0,864
Work Environment (X2)	107	1	5	4,250	0,819
Employee Performance (Y)	107	1	5	4,234	0,853
Job Satisfaction (Z)	107	1	5	4,218	0,828

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on table 8 above, it can be stated as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a range of intervals from 1 to 5 with an average value of 4,267. Therefore, it can be concluded that the average respondents answered agree.
2. The work environment has a range of intervals from 1 to 5 with an average value of 4,250. Therefore, it can be concluded that the average respondents answered agree.
3. Employee performance has a range of intervals from 1 to 5 with an average value of 4,234. Therefore, it can be concluded that the average respondents answered agree.
4. Job satisfaction has a range of intervals from 1 to 5 with an average value of 4.218. Therefore, it can be concluded that the average respondent answered agree.

Coefficient of Determination Test (r^2)

Evaluation of the coefficient of determination (r^2) is used to show how much effect or influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

Table 9
Coefficient of Determination (r^2)

	<i>R Square</i>
Job Satisfaction	0.507
Employee Performance	0.840

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on the table above, it can be seen the R-Square value for the affected variable. The value of R Square on the job satisfaction variable is 0.507 which explains that organizational culture and work environment variables can affect job satisfaction by 84%. Then, the value of R Square on the employee

performance variable is 0.840 which explains that the variables of organizational culture, work environment, and job satisfaction can affect employee performance variables by 84%. Next, the following is the structural models of the current research.

Figure 1 Structural Model
 Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Direct Influence

The direct effect test in this study was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics value and the P-Values value. The research hypothesis for a direct effect can be declared influential if the P-Values value <0.05.

Hypothesis for direct effect:

- H1: Organizational culture has a direct positive influence on employee performance
- H2: Organizational culture has a direct positive influence on job satisfaction
- H3: The work environment has a positive direct influence on employee performance
- H4: The work environment has a positive direct influence on job satisfaction
- H5: Job satisfaction has a positive direct effect on employee performance

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

Decision Criteria:

1. 1. If the P-Value > 0.05 and the T-Statistics value < T table = 1.660) then there is no effect.
2. 2. If the P-Value < 0.05 and the T-Statistics value > T table = 1.660) then there is an effect.

Table 10
Direct Influence Test

Path	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	P Values	Description
Organizational culture -> employee performance	0.326	3.208	0.001	Significant
Organizational culture -> Job satisfaction	0.344	2.997	0.003	Significant
work environment -> employee performance	0.210	2.574	0.010	Significant
work environment -> Job satisfaction	0.456	3.717	0.000	Significant
Job satisfaction -> employee performance	0.515	4.927	0.000	Significant

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

1. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance
The P-Values (0.001) < 0.05 and the T-Statistics (3.208) > T table (1.660), then there is a significant positive effect between organizational culture on employee performance. This explains that the better the organizational culture, the higher the employee performance obtained.
2. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction
The value of P-Values (0.003) < 0.05 and the value of T-Statistics (2.997) > T table (1.660) means that there is a significant positive effect between organizational culture on job satisfaction. This explains that the higher the value of organizational culture, the higher job satisfaction will be.
3. Influence of Work Environment on Employee Performance
The value of P-Values (0.010) < 0.05 and the value of T-Statistics (2.574) > T table (1.660) means that there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on employee performance. This explains that the better the work environment, the higher the employee's performance will be.
4. The Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction
The value of P-Values (0.000) < 0.05 and the value of T-Statistics (3.717) > T table (1.660) means that there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on job satisfaction. This explains that the higher the value of the work environment, the higher the job satisfaction.
5. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance
The value of P-Values (0.000) < 0.05 and the value of T-Statistics (4.927) > T table (1.660) means that there is a significant positive effect between job satisfaction and employee performance. This explains that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the employee's performance

Indirect Influence

The indirect effect test in this study was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics value and the P-Values value. The research hypothesis for an indirect effect can be stated to have an influence if the P-Values value < 0.05 .

Hypothesis for indirect effect:

H6: Organizational culture has an indirect effect on employee performance through job satisfaction

H7: The work environment has an indirect effect on employee performance through job satisfaction.

Decision Criteria:

1. If the P-Value > 0.05 and the T-Statistics value $< T$ table = 1.660) then there is no effect.
2. If the P-Value < 0.05 and the T-Statistics value $> T$ table = 1.660) then there is an effect.

Table 11
Indirect Effect Test

Path	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	T Statistics	P Values	Description
Organizational Culture -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.177	2.453	0.015	Significant
Work Environment -> Job Satisfaction -> Employee Performance	0.235	2.809	0.005	Significant

Source: Processed primary data (2022)

Based on the table above, it is found that:

1. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction
The *original sample* value is 0.177. It is also known that the P-Values (0.015) < 0.05 and the T-Statistics (2.453) $> T$ table (1.660) means that there is a significant positive effect between organizational culture on employee performance through job satisfaction.
2. Influence of Work Environment on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction
The *original sample* value is 0.235. It is also known that the P-Values (0.005) < 0.05 and the T-Statistics (2.809) $> T$ table (1.660), then there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out, seven conclusions are obtained, first, there is a significant positive influence between organizational culture on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.326, and a P-Values value (0.001) < 0.05 and a T-Statistics value. (3,208) $> T$ table (1,660). This explains that the better the organizational culture, the higher the employee's performance. Second, there is a significant positive effect between organizational culture on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.344 and a P-Values value (0.003) < 0.05 and a T-Statistics value (2.997) $> T$ table (1.660). This explains that the higher the value of organizational culture, the higher job satisfaction will be. Third, there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.210 and

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

a P-Values value (0.010) <0.05 and a T-Statistics value (2.574) > T table (1.660). This explains that the higher the value of the work environment, the higher the employee's performance.

Fourth, there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.456 and a P-Values value (0.000) <0.05 and a T-Statistics value (3.717) > T table (1.660). This explains that the higher the value of the work environment, the higher the job satisfaction. Fifth, there is a significant positive effect between job satisfaction on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.515 and a P-Values value (0.000) <0.05 and a T-Statistics value (4.927) > T table (1.660). This explains that the higher the value of job satisfaction, the higher the employee's performance. Sixth, there is a significant positive influence between organizational culture on employee performance through job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.177 and a P-Values value (0.015) <0.05 and a T-Statistics value (2.453) > T table (1.660). And seventh, there is a significant positive effect between the work environment on employee performance through job satisfaction with an original sample value of 0.235 and a P-Values value (0.005) <0.05 and a T-Statistics value (2.809) > T table (1.660).

Acknowledgments: Thank you to the journal editor who has proposed double-blind reviewers, and therefore, this manuscript has been reviewed and accepted.

References

- Andriany, D. (2019). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pada PT. Repex Perdana Internasional (Licensee of Federal Express) Medan. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Kewirausahaan*, 1(1), 392–398.
- Armstrong, M. (2006). *Strategic human resource management*.
- Asharini, N. A., Hardyastuti, S., & Irham, I. (2018). The Impact of Quality of Work Life and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance of PT. Madubaru PG-PS Madukismo. *Agro Ekonomi*, 29(1), 146–159.
- Changgriawan, G. S. (2017). Pengaruh kepuasan kerja dan motivasi kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan di One Way Production. *Agora*, 5(2).
- Devi, E. K. D. (2009). *Analisis Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja dengan Komitmen Organisasional sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi pada Karyawan Outsourcing PT. Semeru Karya Buana Semarang)*. Semarang. Semarang. Tesis. Program Pascasarjana UNDIP.
- Dheviests, T. A., & Riyanto, S. (2020). The Influence of Work Discipline, Self-Efficacy and Work Environment on Employee Performance in the Building Plant D Department at PT Gajah Tunggul Tbk. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(1), 1062–1069.
- Feri, S., Rahmat, A., & Supeno, B. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi, Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening Studi Pada PT. Champion Kurnia Djaja Technologies. *INOBIS: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis Dan Manajemen Indonesia*, 4(1), 134–151.
- Hasibuan, M. S. P., & Hasibuan, H. M. S. P. (2016). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. Bumi Aksara.
- Hendro, T. (2018). Pengaruh Kompensasi Dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Tetap CV. Karya Gemilang. *Agora*, 6(1).
- Jie, I. L. C., Djubair, R. A., & Harun, M. Z. M. (2020). Impact of organizational culture on employees' performance: A study in multinational corporations in Sarawak. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, 10(2), 133–152.
- Krismiyati, K. (2017). Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Pendidikan di SD Negeri Inpres Angkasa Biak. *Jurnal Office*, 3(1), 43–50.
- Kurniawan, N. R. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Pt Pln (Persero) Up3 Kuala Kapuas Kalimantan Tengah. *Jurnal Syntax Transformation*, 1(7), 348–352.
- Kusumastuti, I., ita Kurniawati, N., Satria, D. L., & Wicaksono, D. (2019). Analisis Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dimediasi Oleh Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pada Sp Aluminium di Yogyakarta. *Jurnal REKOMEN (Riset Ekonomi Manajemen)*, 3(1), 43–53.
- Leonardo, E. (2015). Pengaruh pemberian kompensasi terhadap kinerja karyawan pada PT. Kopanitia. *Agora*, 3(2), 28–31.
- Munandar, A. S. (2012). *Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi (pp. 326-332)*. Jakarta: UI Press.
- Napitupulu, I. H. (2018). Organizational culture in management accounting information system: Survey on state-owned enterprises (SOEs) Indonesia. *Global Business Review*, 19(3), 556–571.
- Nugroho, B., Hidayat, W., & Suryoko, S. (2013). Pengaruh lingkungan kerja kepemimpinan dan kompensasi terhadap kepuasan kerja karyawan PT. Kimia Farma Plant Semarang. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 29–39.
- Parashakti, R. D., Fahlevi, M., Ekhsan, M., & Hadinata, A. (2020). The influence of work environment and competence on motivation and its impact on employee performance in health sector. *3rd Asia Pacific International Conference of Management and Business Science (AICMBS 2019)*, 259, 267.

The effect of organizational culture and work environment on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediation: Case at pt teknologi abadi sejahtera (Bayu Kurniawan Azlen, I Ketut R. Sudiartha, Henry Eryanto)

- Pranitasari, D. (2019). *Keterikatan kerja dosen sebagai kunci keberhasilan perguruan tinggi*. Deepublish.
- Putri, S. M., Swasono, E., & Baehaki, I. (2020). Pengaruh budaya organisasi dan gaya kepemimpinan terhadap kinerja karyawan melalui kepuasan kerja sebagai variabel intervening. *Commodities, Journal of Economic and Business*, 1(2), 137–158.
- Rivai, V., & Mulyadi, D. (2012). *Kepimpinan dan Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo.
- Rizky, P., Wahjusaputri, S., & Wibowo, A. A. (2020). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Pizza Hut Wilayah Jakarta Timur. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Widya Wiwaha Program Magister Manajemen*, 7(2), 105–112.
- Robbins, S. P. (2002). *Prinsip-prinsip perilaku organisasi*.
- Rozarie, C. V. R. A. De, & Indonesia, J. T. K. R. (2017). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*.
- Sharma, P. (2017). Organizational culture as a predictor of job satisfaction: The role of age and gender. *Management-Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*, 22(1), 35–48.
- Taheri, R. H., Miah, M. S., & Kamaruzzaman, M. (2020). Impact of working environment on job satisfaction. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(6).
- Weiss, H. M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: Separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12(2), 173–194.
- Wicaksono, W., Suyatin, S., Sunarsi, D., Affandi, A., & Herling, H. (2021). Pengaruh Pelatihan, Motivasi Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT Bank Mandiri, Tbk Di Jakarta. *JENIUS (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia)*, 5(1), 220–237.
- Wijaya, I. K. (2018). Pengaruh kepuasan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan cv bukit sanomas. *Agora*, 6(2).
- Yuliantari, K., & Prasasti, I. (2020). Pengaruh lingkungan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada LLDIKTI wilayah III Jakarta. *Widya Cipta: Jurnal Sekretari dan Manajemen*, 4(1), 76–82.